

Data Fusion of Low-Cost Sensor Networks and Dispersion Models for High-Resolution Urban Air Quality Mapping

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ABSTRACT

Climate change is expected to alter meteorological drivers of air pollution, influencing the formation, transport, and exposure patterns of key pollutants [1]. Low-cost sensor (LCS) networks provide the high-resolution, real-time data needed for risk management, but only when supported by robust calibration. Combining these sensors with dispersion models bridges spatial gaps, enhancing both exposure assessment and decision-making [2]. This study presents a high-resolution air-quality monitoring and mapping framework for the TÜBİTAK Gebze Campus, leveraging data from a pilot field study conducted between February and May 2024. The objective is to establish a localized dispersion model integrating real-time measurements from six LCSs using advanced spatial modeling techniques. The study used sensors to measure key pollutants, including nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), ozone (O₃), and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), as well as critical meteorological parameters, including wind speed and direction, temperature, pressure, and humidity. LCSs developed in a previous study employ AI-based calibration to correct for environmental influences, with performance validated against CEN/TS 17660:1 standard through a year-long co-location study at four reference stations across different seasons [3, 4, 5]. Strategic sensor placement enabled the characterization of diverse micro-environments, from high-traffic gates to sensitive areas such as schools. Preliminary analysis showed that NO₂ peaks correlated with traffic hours, while O₃ and PM_{2.5} levels were influenced by photochemical reactions and regional transport from the Gulf of Izmit. A Gaussian-based dispersion model specifically for NO₂, tailored to campus topography, was implemented to refine spatial accuracy. Model outputs and sensor data were integrated via data fusion to produce hourly, street-level maps. Results demonstrate that this integrated approach offers a robust, cost-effective solution for local air quality management.

Keywords — *Low-cost sensor networks, air quality dispersion modeling, data fusion*

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